

REVERSIBILITY OF ALDOL CONDENSATION

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The reversible change : acetone \rightleftharpoons diacetone alcohol is studied quantitatively and chemically by using magnesiummethyl iodide which gives methane with diacetone alcohol only. The change is catalysed by OH' ions. At 23° and in about 10% aqueous alkaline solution the equilibrium ratio, diacetone alcohol : acetone, comes to 26 : 74.

The reversibility of aldol condensation was recognised by Koelichen (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 33, 1, 129) who observed that transformation of acetone into diacetone alcohol was reversible.

The reaction is catalysed by OH' ions and a quantitative study has shown that the equilibrium proportion of the components is independent of their initial concentrations or that of the OH' ions.

The change acetone \rightleftharpoons diacetone alcohol was studied by following a change in some physical property, such as (i) change of volume in a dilatometer (Koelichen, *loc. cit.*), (ii) change in refractive index (Davis and Burrows, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 311), (iii) heat change recorded by a specially constructed calorimeter (Sturtevant, *ibid.*, 1937, 59, 1522).

The change can also be followed chemically provided it could be arrested when desired and a reagent is used which reacts with one of the components, quantitatively in a few seconds. In the experiments described in this paper the change was arrested by neutralising the alkali supplying OH' ions, and the reagent was magnesiummethyl iodide which was found to evolve one molecule of methane with one molecule of diacetone alcohol, and which gave no gas with acetone. Since the change was followed in aqueous alkaline solution, it was necessary to remove water completely from the mixture of components before addition of the Grignard reagent. This was achieved by their extraction from aqueous solution by toluene and by drying the extract over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The methane evolved was measured in a Lunge nitrometer.

As the measurement of a physical property (volume) of the components was the basis of Koelichen's method, he used minimum amount of water (25 g. of a mixture of diacetone alcohol and acetone to which 1 c.c. of aqueous alkali of strength 0.2N, 0.1N and 0.05N was added). The value of the ratio, diacetone alcohol : acetone at equilibrium at 25°, extrapolated to 0% water, came to be 16 : 84.

In the present case the equilibrium was observed from both sides in aqueous solution by starting with one of the components in about 10% concentration (90% water) containing N/75 and N/100 alkali. The equilibrium proportion at 23° observed from either side came to 26 : 74 (average) and it was independent of the initial concentration of the component or that of OH' ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method used for estimating diacetone alcohol by observing the volume of methane evolved by the action of Grignard reagent on a known weight of it, is the one recommended by Tschugaeff and Zerivitinoff (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2027) for the determination of "active hydrogen".

The reagent was prepared by dissolving magnesium in methyl iodide diluted with pure di-isoamyl ether, previously distilled over sodium dust. This was introduced in the short limb of a λ tube, the long limb containing the mixture of the components completely freed from water. The vertical limb of the λ tube was connected through pressure tubing to the measuring tube of the Lunge nitrometer filled with brine. Air from the λ tube was replaced by nitrogen bubbled through alkaline pyrogallic acid, followed by strong sulphuric acid. The λ tube was dipped in a water-bath kept at 23°. By tilting, the contents in the limbs of λ tube were brought together. Methane was quickly evolved and the displaced nitrogen was collected in the measuring tube of the nitrometer and its volume recorded.

The extraction of diacetone alcohol (or a mixture of it with acetone) from aqueous solution by toluene and the removal of moisture from the extract were done as follows. A definite volume of the aqueous solution (1 c.c. by a standard pipette) was poured over ammonium sulphate (1 g.) in a test tube and the resulting pasty mass was extracted thrice with 3 c.c. of toluene each time. The total extract was decanted off, the ammonium sulphate was finally rinsed with 1 c.c. of toluene and the rinsing added to the extract. The total extract after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was transferred to the long limb of the λ tube and was then brought in contact with the reagent. As will be seen from Table I, the volume of methane evolved from a certain weight of diacetone alcohol extracted from its aqueous solution is equal to the volume of the gas obtained from the same weight of the pure compound. In experiments with pure acetone and with acetone extracted from aqueous solution no evolution of gas was observed (Table I, B).

TABLE I

Wt. of diacetone alcohol.	Vol. of CH ₄ evolved at N.T.P. from pure compound.	Vol. of CH ₄ observed at N.T.P. from the compound extracted from aq. soln..	Calc. vol.	Obs./calc.
A. Diacetone alcohol.				
1. 0.0296	6.8 c.c.	6.8 c.c.	6.0 c.c.	1.1
2. 0.0358	7.4	7.4	6.9	1.07
3. 0.0476	10.1	—	9.3	1.08
4. 0.0636	13.1	13.1	12.3	1.06
5. 0.1000	—	20.3	19.1	1.06
B. Acetone.				
1. 0.0358	0.0	0.0	0.0	
2. 0.0476	0.0	0.0	0.0	
3. 0.0296	0.0	0.0	0.0	

In each case the observed volume of methane is slightly higher than the theoretical. The ratio between the two (excluding case 1) varies between 1.06 and 1.08. This may be taken therefore as correction factor (Table I, A).

The experimental procedure in following the change acetone \rightleftharpoons diacetone alcohol in aqueous solution containing alkali of known strength was as follows.

One of the two components was weighed accurately in a normal flask (20 c.c.). Water was added, followed by a measured volume of normal alkali, the solution was brought to the mark and the flask left in a water-bath kept at 23°. At definite intervals 1 c.c. of the solution was pipetted out and poured over ammonium sulphate (1 g.) to which one drop of strong sulphuric acid was added to neutralise the alkali. The extraction with toluene and drying of the extract were carried out as already described.

TABLE II

Acetone.

N/100-Alkali (NaOH). Temp. = 23°. Pressure = 750 mm. Wt. of acetone for 20 c.c. = 2.0126 g. 1 c.c. = 0.1006 g.

No.	Time.	CH ₄ evolved.	% Diacetone alcohol.*
1	0.0 hr.	1.9 c.c.	7.47
2	0.5	2.5	10.58
3	1.0	3.0	13.08
4	1.5	3.6	15.88
5	2.0	4.1	17.04
6	2.5	5.0	21.40
7	3.0	5.8	25.98

TABLE III

Diacetone alcohol.

Wt. of diacetone alcohol for 20 c.c. = 2.0082 g. 1 c.c. = 0.1004 g. Other factors, same as in Table II.

No.	Time.	CH ₄ evolved	% Diacetone alcohol*
1	0.0 hr.	20.8 c.c.	87.60
1	0.5	20.0	80.80
3	1.0	17.7	77.10
4	1.5	15.4	62.61
5	2.0	14.0	60.09
6	2.5	12.8	53.73
7	3.0	11.2	47.66
8	5.75	5.8	25.98
9	21.5	5.8	25.98

*After applying correction factor.

Tables II and III show that the same equilibrium proportion of the components, namely diacetone alcohol (26%) and acetone (74%) is reached under the experimental conditions by starting the change from either side.

TABLE IV

Acetone.

N/75-Alkali (NaOH). = Temp. 23°. Pressure = 750 mm. Wt. of acetone for 20 c.c. = 2.0104 g. 1 c.c. = 0.1005 g.

No.	Time	Vol.	% Diacetone alcohol.
1	0.0 hr.	1.1 c.c.	5.14
2	0.5	1.8	7.7
3	1.5	3.3	14.48
4	2.0	4.2	13.31
5	2.5	5.1	22.63
6	2.0	5.9	25.98
7	21.0	5.9	25.98

TABLE V

Diacetone alcohol.

Weight of diacetone alcohol for 20 c.c. = 2.0104 g. 1 c.c. = 0.1005 g. Other conditions, same as in Table IV.

No.	Time	Vol. of CH ₄	% Diacetone alcohol*
1	0.0	21.4 c.c.	91.58
2	0.5	19.1	81.3
3	1.0	16.8	71.49
4	1.5	14.6	62.15
5	2.0	12.3	52.9
6	2.5	10.0	43.0
7	3.0	7.7	34.1
8	3.5	6.6	25.98

Tables IV and V show that whereas by increase in the strength of alkali from *N*/100 to *N*/75 the time required to reach the equilibrium point from the side of acetone remains unaffected. This increase favours reaching equilibrium more quickly from the side of diacetone alcohol.

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